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FEASIBLE FUTURE OF APPLYING BLOCK CHAIN TECHNOLOGY TO DIGITALIZED NATIONAL ECONOMY

Abstract: *The article discusses the implementation of blockchain as a technology of the future, which will make it possible to save finances, make financial schemes transparent, block the very possibility of committing illegal actions in the economic sphere. The author's position and proposals on the future of blockchain for the digitalization of the national economy are proposed.*

Keywords: *Blockchain technology, under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan National Agency for Project Management, e-Government, artificial intelligence, Single interactive public services portal, Digital Trust Fund, investment projects.*

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ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ БЛОКЧЕЙН В ЦИФРОВОЙ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ

Аннотация: *В статье рассмотрены вопросы внедрения блокчейна как технологии будущего, которая даст возможность экономить финансы, сделает прозрачными финансовые схемы, перекроет саму*

возможность совершать противоправные действия в экономической сфере. Предлагается авторская позиция и предложения по будущему блокчейна для цифровизации национальной экономики.

Ключевые слова: *Технология блокчейн, Национальное агентство по управлению проектами при Президенте Республики Узбекистан, электронное правительство, искусственный интеллект, Единый портал интерактивных государственных услуг, цифровой трастовый фонд, инвестиционные проекты.*

Introduction

A number of policies are being chosen to improve the national economy, strengthen macroeconomic stability, attract foreign investment, modernize industry and build production using modern high technologies. The analysis of current practice requires the timely implementation of tasks on comprehensive socio-economic development, the timely identification and elimination of problems that hinder the ongoing reforms in our country. In particular, the development of major financial projects of national importance lack of a unified project management system to ensure quality organization, coordination, monitoring and control of the launch and implementation process, insufficient implementation of advanced information and communication technologies in the management process, which allows to quickly monitor the pace and effectiveness of these projects; low level of transparency in the development and implementation of investment projects, misuse of funds in this regard, leading to various abuses we are witnessing that. Also, the lack of a single information platform integrated with the databases of government agencies, businesses, state-owned enterprises and organizations, which ensure the transparency of the public procurement process, today hinders the introduction of blockchain technology in the economy puts it as a major issue [1-8]. Exact blockchain all that is carried out as a result of the introduction of technology into all sectors of the national economy expediency, justification of financial investment projects and analyze and evaluate profitability, increase their value and ongoing work to identify signs of other abuses would have served to increase its efficiency.

Literature review

The development of the digital economy is closely bonded with the issues of further restructuring of the economy, public administration, as well as the creation of new models of interaction between the state, business and the population based on digital technologies.

By E. Brynjolfssonva and B. Kohinlar, the issue of digitalization of the economy was first discussed in the mid-1990s as the subject of discussion, and the first definitions were given, recognizing in these definitions as a means of bringing businesses and consumers together in the virtual world.

By the end of the 1990s, the analysis focused on ways to increase economic efficiency in enterprises, mainly through the use of the Internet in the economy. The impact of the Internet resource in the process of digitization of the economy has been widely assessed, and comments on its hidden potential have been made.

Began to be considered [1-14]. Issues related to the problems that underlie the digital economy, the mechanism of transition to the digital economy, and the hashing functions, which are an important element of cryptography, have been provided. Then, the logic of the transition from cryptography to digital currencies, of cryptocurrencies

The main types and their properties are reflected in the works of academician S. Gulyamov found in [3].

Research methodology

Development, renewal and rational economic reforms to modernize as a result, today the development of an innovative economy is being achieved. In particular, corporate financial management in the activities of business entities effective implementation of the "blockchain" in the implementation of financial planning issues of using technologies. The national economy the role and importance of the use of blockchain technology in digitization The following methods were used in the study.

1. E-electronics in the digitization of the corporate financial management process the importance of e-commerce in commerce was studied.
2. Achieved as a result of digitization of the national economy efficiency trends were described.
3. Analysis of the practice of using blockchain technologies at the national level was found.

Analysis and results

It should be noted that in this direction to date A number of measures have been developed. Including Korea on December 17, 2019 at Sejong city, Republic of Korea, with the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan National Agency for Project Management and Public Administration of the Republic of Korea and between the Ministry of Security on e-government and the digital economy An agreement on the opening of a joint center was signed. According to the agreement Korea for the development of e-government of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2 million dollars in non-discriminatory assistance. Also, a national agency delegation held December 5-6, 2019 in Haikou (PRC) participated in the International Forum on Economics and Blockchain Technology. Forum in China for the development and introduction of innovative technologies (artificial intelligence, big data, Internet of Things, blockchain) and the implementation of promising projects based on them, mainly in the real sector (industry, agriculture, medicine) Hainan Free Economic Zone, where the first specialized pilot zone was established was held in the territory of Agency delegation "Hainan Resort Software Community Group", Hainan Free Trade Zone Blockchain Pilot Zone with special zone directorates and Innovation Intelligence Union Group Company, Huobi Group, WeiZhongJie held working meetings with representatives of companies, "Oxford-Hainan Blockchain Research Institute "and innovative high school got acquainted with the activities of " iSchool ".

Agency of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2019 3 PQ-3832 "Digital Economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan In accordance with the Resolution "On development measures", Uzbekistan

In the field of irrigation of the republic with the Ministry of Water Resources of the Republic creating conditions for the introduction and development of the digital economy is implementing the measure on Customized intelligent system Implements LPWan and Internet of Things technology and WI-FI, GSM communication from any device (tablet, smartphone, laptop), stationary via channels managed using computers and set up a dispatching system does. The modules and sensors included in the system are autonomous power supply and with built-in software, up to 3 km by the central block the range of motion is controlled by a radio communication channel.

E-Government and Digital under the National Agency for Project Management Economic Project Management Center, Single integrator UZINFOCOM and Extra-budgetary Pension under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan by the Foundation, a new interactive that provides complete information on retirement / retirement launched the civil service. Through a single interactive public services portal The following information can be found online: pension (benefit) amount, date of appointment, payment period, length of service, type of pension, selected period

on the amount of payments, as well as accrued and uncalculated length of service data. All the necessary information is added in real time will be available without documents. This service is the only interactive public services Listed in the "Social Security" section of the portal, individuals (pensioners) are provided free of charge [4]. In addition, "Electronic Single interactive public services for the development of the "government" system An updated version of the portal has been launched. In the new version of the portal users are required to have a single identification system with all public services will be able to meet without authorization. The portal is its own users to use 166 types of public services, search for relevant information, solve business problems and solve many possibilities reveals a wide range of possibilities in finding. As mentioned above, in the portal changes in new technologies in the socio-economic spheres of the country introduction, access to public services and business development associated with the creation of additional favorable conditions for.

The Agency is responsible for monitoring the implementation of investment projects and monitoring "automated information system. This investment and infrastructure in the country as a result of the system Investment and timely implementation of local programs for the implementation of projects and quality performance monitoring will be possible. Also the system has the following capabilities: accounting for projects, their implementation automation of control and monitoring processes; project deadlines, control over the budget, goals and indicators; investments, including the attraction and development of foreign direct investment formation of reliable data on volumes; in the implementation of projects identification of risks for timely commissioning of facilities; from investment in the next period, to achieve the targets provided for in the project documents to follow.

Development of the digital economy, the system of public administration further structural change, as well as digitalization between the state, business and the population issues of creating new models of technology-based interaction closely related to. It is the digitization of the economy that is at least 30 percent of GDP allowing a sharp reduction in corruption in society while ensuring a percentage increase The head of state Sh.

Mirziyoyev also noted that he could give [6]. Also, the Project Management under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan e-government and digital economy projects under the national agency Control Center of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 10, 2019 №PF- E-government and digital economy projects in accordance with Decree No. 5624 Management Center State Unitary Enterprise was established. Areas of activity of the center: Development of e-government system and Digital Uzbekistan-2030 in the field of information and communication technologies in the framework of the program future strategic directions of programs in the framework of project implementation, development of a single approach, mechanism and stages; systematic monitoring of the status of project development and implementation as well as rating the effectiveness of the introduction of information and communication technologies in the activities of government agencies and organizations under the program formation; "smart" and other promising technologies in various sectors of the economy, as well as the introduction of large-scale data processing technologies formation of conceptual and methodological basis; e-government system in accordance with the requirements of international standards collection, processing and processing of statistical data describing the level of development maintaining an accounting system; Infrastructure of "e-government" system, Unified Republic of Uzbekistan an interactive public services portal and for the provision of public services Single billing system, which calculates the amount of paid state duties and fees, including further development on the terms of public-private partnership supply vs. marked.

Supporting the development of the digital economy "Digital Trust" Fund of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev 2018 2 Digital Trust Fund established in accordance with the Resolution No. PP-3927 of September was found. Development of projects in the field of digital economy and blockchain and mobilizes investment to implement, human resources in the field of blockchain and Supports training activities for startups and organizes cooperation with foreign and international organizations in the field of cryptocurrencies and blockchain helps to achieve

Funds in the field of blockchain, crypto-assets, digital economy purchase of shares and stakes in the charter capital of companies, startups allocating grants and loans to support the digital economy to implement measures such as development.

The basic principles of digitization of the economy and material resources are presented, among which the importance of resources such as human capital, the creation of new business models, various levels of technological armament. Use of blockchain technology in the process of digitizing the economy is an important stage. Blockchain technology is implemented using these blocks were incremental transactions, consisting of a sequence of blocks and pages can be recognized as a special ledger. Each in this special notebook the serial number and signature of a block are displayed. Blockchain technology any information entered into the database as an achievement may be modified only with the 100% consent of all users logged in is The ratio to the infrastructure provider is not required.

Geollection of the practice of using blockchain technologies at the national level As we have seen, cryptocurrency payments, property registration, voting technology, identification, delivery

chain management, health, power of attorney voting, legal implementation of state registration of individuals, in the system of taxation and the state introduced into pension implementation systems [6]. Of course, series during the introduction of blockchain technologies in the digitization process problematic situations can also be observed. Including financial economics full coverage of the process requires a student tooth, lack of human resources and high need for continuous increase, constant uninterrupted power supply supply requirements, the level of availability of Internet resources to be high. However, the introduction of this technology in a number of countries The types of services provided by education, including medical, financial services to significantly reduce the amount of costs for the species, their quality can lead to a sharp increase in overall coverage. fully ensures the operational independence of this technology. Also Blockchain Any participant involved in the technology behaves independently be able to conduct an independent audit of the area of interest. This As a result of the operation of the technology, any operation can be carried out quickly and cheaply. It will be possible to continuously optimize transaction costs.

If we look at the world practice, it is these technologies that are applied to the economy The introduction of new, in addition to accelerating its digitization process creation of business models, acceleration of technological and revolutionary processes, to accelerate the process of transformation of various industries and industries, production to increase efficiency, the process of creating added value has a significant impact on optimization.

Conclusions and suggestions.

In conclusion, it should be noted that Uzbekistan is a national from blockchain technologies in accelerating the process of digitization of the economy should be fully transferred to the practice of use. Also: use of new information technologies in the digitization process local through the involvement of foreign experts in order to increase the speed achieving short-term capacity building;

Establish periodicity of special trainings for IT specialists programming taking into account the specific directions of the national economy to accelerate the process of adaptation of products to industries; content that supplies venture and acceleration software products to the industry, event halls, which could operate in coworking centers specialists, personnel who can control the activities of data centers training, retraining and continuous training opening an IT academy that can demonstrate; Providing a special package of benefits for the development of IT business;

Development of a mechanism for preferential lending to IT projects, including in Europe introduction of minimum lending limits based on experience; intellectual property or royalty licensing legislation improvement, etc.

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ЭЪЛОН

Хурматли ҳамкасабалар “Al-Ferganus” нашриёти ва “Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali” электрон журнали Ўзбекистон таълим хизматлари бозорида ўзининг фаолиятини бошлаганлигини маълум қиламиз.

Ажойиб имкониятдан сиз биринчилар қаторида фойдаланиб илмий нашрларингизни чоп этишингиз мумкин.

“Al-Ferganus” нашриётимиз томонидан Сиз тақдим этган дарслик, ўқув қўлланма, монография ва илмий рисолаларга ISBN, Doi халқаро рақамли идентификаторларни бириктириш, уларнинг электрон замонавий андозадаги муқовалар ва ишланмаларнинг электрон макетини яратиш, нашриётда эълон қилинган ишларни электрон ахборот нашрларида жойлаштириш хизматлари кўрсатилади.

Бизнинг нашриётимизнинг бошқа нашриётлардан фарқи шундаки, тезкор ва сифатли хизмат кўрсатамиз ҳамда энг асосийси биз Сизнинг ишларингизни Алишер Навоий номидаги Ўзбекистон Миллий кутубхонаси ва Россия Миллий кутубхонаси фондларига бепул жойлашга шунингдек, Россия илмий иқтибослик индекси (РИНЦ ва E - library) платформасига, CrossRef базаларига шартнома асосида жойлаштиришга кўмаклашамиз.

“Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali” ISSN 2181-2357 электрон журнали ҳам ўз фаолиятини бошламоқда. Бизнинг журналда Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий аттестация комиссиясининг куйидаги ихтисосликлари физика-математика, кимё, биология, геология-минералогия, техника, қишлоқ хўжалиги,

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Совместно с Ферганским политехническим институтом запущен проект электронного научного журнала «Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali - International Journal of Theoretical and Practical Research. Международный журнал теоретических и прикладных исследований».

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